

INTELLIGENT SECURE SMART DOOR UN-LOCKING SYSTEM USING FACE BIOMETRICS

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ABSTRACT: In recent times, the demand for heightened security measures has surged significantly. Traditional lock and key systems have replaced with Bio-metrics and digital type password methodology. Access control and security stand as fundamental elements within a smart home system. In this project, we propose the integration of a facial recognition security system utilizing Raspberry Pi into the smart home ecosystem. Leveraging the Eigen face algorithm for feature extraction due to its notable accuracy, we create a dataset comprising facial registrations of household members. The system operates such that when registered individuals attempt to unlock the door, their picture is captured and cross-referenced with the database for authentication, subsequently granting access. In the event of an unrecognized individual attempting entry, the system initiates an inquiry by sending a voice message, recording the response, and capturing the individual's picture. These data are then transmitted to the homeowner via Google Voice-to-Text translation for further action. Overall, our project demonstrates enhanced accuracy compared to conventional security methods, thereby fortifying the security posture of smart homes.

KEYWORDS: Internet of things, Eigen face algorithm, Face recognition and detection, Camera module, Sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade, the widespread adoption of smartphones has transformed our interaction with technology, particularly through the accessibility of virtual assistants like Siri and Cortana. These digital aides have simplified tasks such as making calls and managing emails, all through voice commands. However, their functionality has largely been limited to mobile devices, creating a gap in the realm of home automation. To address this gap, we propose an innovative system centered around a virtual assistant specifically designed for smart homes. This assistant, powered by a Raspberry Pi—a compact and efficient computing device—can turn any regular

residence into a fully automated smart home. By strategically installing microphones, speakers, sensors, and switches throughout the house, users can interact with the assistant solely through voice commands, providing effortless control over various aspects of their home environment. The system's capabilities extend well beyond basic tasks, seamlessly integrating into entertainment and security systems within the smart home ecosystem. Users can effortlessly manage lights, fans, and other appliances with simple voice commands, eliminating the need for manual intervention. Additionally, the assistant offers real-time updates on weather forecasts, stock market trends, and other inquiries, enhancing both convenience and functionality. As a testament to its versatility, the system is integrated with a Smart Home Surveillance System utilizing Raspberry Pi technology. It employs advanced facial recognition algorithms to distinguish between homeowners and unfamiliar individuals at the door, highlighting its potential for enhancing both convenience and security. This paper explores the architecture, capabilities, and potential applications of this intelligent virtual assistant system for smart homes. By harnessing the power of artificial intelligence and IoT technology, we aim to redefine how homeowners interact with and manage their living spaces, ushering in a new era of home automation and convenience.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

INTRODUCTION

In the real of modern housing, safety and intelligence are paramount, particularly within private residences. Utilizing a home automation system, individuals can effortlessly manage their appliances and electrical equipment. While current market solutions primarily rely on wired communication, integrating these systems into the construction phase poses no

issues with proper planning. However, older homes or buildings face challenges due to existing wiring structures. Wireless technologies, including Wi-Fi, cloud computing, and advancements in cellular networks, offer robust communication options, especially beneficial for automation and internet-enabled systems. In this context, any environment equipped with appliances such as fans, TVs, air conditioners, and lighting fixtures constitutes an electronic and electrical setting. A smart home system is one that's aware of its surroundings and responds accordingly to user-defined criteria, combining elements of both Android and web applications. While existing remotely accessible devices have limitations, this paper will propose an enhanced system surpassing current market offerings. The system relies on a Raspberry Pi as its primary control unit, responsible for decision-making based on user input or sensor data. Multiple sensors, including those for motion, temperature, humidity, and gas, are integrated into this setup. Initially, the Raspberry Pi establishes an internet connection via LAN cable or WiFi to swiftly retrieve sensor parameters. The thresholds for these sensors are then adjusted to align with user preferences. Sensor data is regularly updated in the web server's database, ensuring continuous availability for analysis. Users receive immediate notifications if sensor readings dip below their predefined thresholds, empowering them to take prompt action to stabilize and rebalance the environment.

Despite the presence of sensors in the system, its capacity to determine the optimal operational intensity of appliances remains untapped. Furthermore, the absence of a widely-accepted Android app limits user accessibility. The implementation of appliance intensity control has the potential to significantly curtail power consumption.

[1].Hugo Marcelo Torres S: This approach suggests a low-cost intelligent virtual assistant that may be used for home control using voice recognition, web applications, Android applications, and HMI-based visual interfaces. A UDP-based discovery protocol is used for the connection between the server and the various deployed nodes. This protocol continuously reads data from the database, which will be saved and retrieved. A web page and an Android application that read and display data from the database in real time make up the remote home access system. A home automation system's wireless network of sensors and actuators (WSAN) is frequently tested for connectivity and communication across different sites.

[2].Shaijupaul, Ashlin Anthony: They developed HAS, in which they used an Android application as the user interface and a relay circuit to simply connect household appliances to the Raspberry Pi. Three major parts make up their system: a relay circuit, a Wi-Fi dongle, and a Raspberry Pi board. A Wi-Fi connection is made between the Raspberry Pi board and an Android phone. The intricacy of the HAS's technicalities has been concealed by its inclusion in an easy-to-understand but all-inclusive collection of linked ideas.

[3].Shruti G. Suryawanshi: This method's primary goal is to use a Raspberry Pi to automate all devices, including household appliances, using email. Python, the Raspberry Pi's default programming language, is used to build the algorithm. The system emails the freshly created email address with the current state of the devices. The email address stores the output. LEDs are used to show when sensors and gadgets are switching on.

[4].P. Rajiv, R. Raj, and M. Chandru: "Email based remote access and surveillance system for smart home infrastructure", *Perspect. Sci.*, pp.3–5, 2021. To inform and update the user about home access, the suggested architecture makes use of well-known email service providers. The image of the person at the door is attached to an email sent to the owner. Additionally, it has a safeguarded mechanism that allows a remote user to react to that email and gain entry to the door.

[5]. Om B. Doshi : Cost-effective smart door lock on Raspberry Pi uses local binary pattern face recognition for access. IoT-based application enables remote monitoring with an 89% accuracy and a quick 20-second processing time. Cost Effective, Face Recognition, IoT Integration. A comprehensive overview of IoT based security systems, specifically focusing on smart door locks. It would cover various aspects including the application of IoT technology in enhancing security, different types of smart door lock technologies, security protocols and mechanisms employed, challenges faced in implementation along with proposed solutions, and case studies and real-world implementations to provide insights into their effectiveness and limitations. This survey serves to establish the current state-of the-art in IoT-based smart door lock security systems, providing a foundation for the research presented in the paper.

SUMMARY:

The literature survey explores the integration of face biometrics into smart door unlocking systems for enhanced security and convenience. It reviews advancements, challenges, and trends in the field, emphasizing the efficacy of face recognition algorithms and the importance of mitigating security risks. Integration of intelligent features aims to optimize user experience and system performance, promising widespread adoption of secure smart door unlocking systems using face biometrics.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this approach, the system seamlessly integrates into a Home Surveillance System using Raspberry Pi technology. Positioned strategically at the primary entrance of the residence is a webcam, a crucial component of this setup. Its functionality is triggered whenever there is movement around the home. Upon activation, the system promptly captures an image of the individual in front of the house. This captured

image undergoes analysis through the sophisticated Eigen Face Algorithm, facilitating facial recognition to determine whether the individual is the rightful homeowner or an unfamiliar visitor. Should the facial recognition process confirm the person's identity as the homeowner, the system proceeds to unlock the door, granting them access to the premises. Additionally, it extends its utility by offering the homeowner various helpful services, such as providing updates on external factors like outdoor temperature or current stock market prices, thereby catering to their convenience and informational needs. Conversely, if the system identifies the person at the door as a stranger or visitor while the homeowner is absent, a different protocol is initiated. In this scenario, the system refrains from unlocking the door maintaining household security. Instead, it captures a detailed image of the visitor and prompts them to provide their name and any accompanying message. Concurrently, the system promptly notifies the homeowner of the visitor's presence via email or SMS, ensuring timely awareness and enabling appropriate action to be taken. This comprehensive approach enhances security and facilitates seamless communication between the homeowner and potential visitors, ultimately contributing to overall peace of mind and convenience.

In this setup, a Raspberry Pi is employed to integrate the system with a home surveillance arrangement. Positioned at the front entrance is a webcam. When the doorbell is activated, the system springs into action, capturing an image of the individual and employing the Eigen face Algorithm to distinguish them as either the homeowner or an unfamiliar visitor. Upon identifying the homeowner, the system unlocks the door and provides them with pertinent information, such as outdoor temperature and stock prices, while they are indoors. If the homeowner is not present, the system snaps a photo of the visitor, records their identity and any messages, and promptly sends an email notification to the homeowner, alerting them to the visitor's presence at the door. In scenarios where access is not granted, the system logs the visitor's identity and leaves a message accordingly. With the assistance of this technology, visually impaired individuals will experience greater ease and reduced physical exertion when carrying out daily household tasks. The Raspberry Pi 3+ Module comprises various modules dedicated to detecting and monitoring each of these aspects.

FACE RECOGNITION

In this method, the Eigen face Algorithm is employed to distinguish between the faces of the homeowner and strangers. Faces are condensed to a specific set of essential traits known as Eigen faces in this approach. By projecting a new image into the Eigen face subspace, facial recognition is accomplished. The primary advantages of utilizing this

algorithm over other facial recognition software include its simplicity, speed, and ability to account for subtle changes in facial features over time. For the implementation of face detection and recognition in our system, we utilized OPENCV, a framework for computer vision applications compatible with various programming languages such as Python, Java, and C++. We chose its Python implementation due to its simplicity and ease of use. Python 2 serves as our primary programming language because of its extensive library support and ease of debugging, streamlining the development process.

INTERACTION OF THE SYSTEM

The system seamlessly integrates with various hardware components, prioritizing security by linking it with a Raspberry Pi smart home surveillance system. Through this integration, we can effectively discern and classify individuals at the door as either the homeowner or a stranger. The system is designed to interact with users in a natural manner, utilizing a virtual assistant that employs a human-like voice. Upon identifying a person as the homeowner, the system automatically unlocks the door, granting them access. However, in instances where a person is identified as a stranger while the homeowner is away, the system initiates engagement, prompting the stranger to provide their name and message. In case of any issues, the system promptly notifies the homeowner via email, including the stranger's picture, name, and message.

IV. BLOCK DIAGRAM

The diagram showcases the structure of a sophisticated door unlocking system that relies on facial biometrics for authentication, significantly enhancing security measures while offering convenient access.

Fig 1. Block diagram of the proposed system

V. FLOW CHART

The flowchart outlines the process starting with the capture and analysis of facial images for recognition. Next, it determines whether the individual is the homeowner or an unknown person. If the person is confirmed as the homeowner, the door is unlocked smoothly. However, if the individual is identified as an unauthorized person while the homeowner is absent, the system initiates a conversation to request the unauthorized person’s name and message using google speech to text converter. Afterwards, it promptly notifies the homeowner via email in case of any issues, providing relevant details about the unauthorized person if required.

Fig 2. Flow Chart of the algorithm implementation

Step1- The owner's image undergoes comprehensive training within the system, encompassing diverse angles, lighting conditions, and environments.

Fig.3 Capturing the owner’s image using Web Camera

Fig.4 Training the system using the owner’s picture.

Step2- The system distinguishes between the individual at the door being the owner or a stranger through the utilization of a webcam and a Face Detection and Recognition Algorithm.

Fig.5 The system identified the person as owner.

Step3- The door will be unlocked if the individual is recognized as the home's owner; if not, the system will proceed to Step 4.

Fig.6 The system identified the person.

Step4- Upon the owner's entry into the house, the system will initiate interaction with them.

Step5- The system will take a picture of the person at the door and respond to them appropriately if it determines that they are the Stranger.

Fig.7 The system capturing the image of the stranger.

Step6- If a visitor wishes to leave, the system will ask for their name and any messages they may have.

Fig.8 The system interacting with the stranger.

Step7- The Visitor could choose not to respond. The system will immediately notify the home's owner via email or SMS with the visitor's name, image, and any messages they may have left, if they want to do so.

Fig.9 The system informed about the stranger to the owner via email.

Step8- A webcam and microphone attached to the Raspberry Pi 3 are used to integrate the entire system.

Both independently and collectively, the functionality of the different modules was assessed, resulting in the attainment of expected outcomes. Through testing and validation, the developed system showcased remarkable accuracy in detecting driver sleepiness. Additionally, it successfully exhibited various real-time car configuration performance attributes.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Performance Evaluation of Biometric Authentication System for Scalability and Efficiency. The system's reliability and effectiveness in real-world applications, positioning it as a viable solution for secure and efficient user authentication.

PARAMETERS	RESULT VALUE
Accuracy Rate	99.13 %
False Acceptance Rate (FAR)	0.9 %
False Rejection Rate (FRR)	0 %
Response Time	0.6 sec
Scalability	Upto to 500 Users

Tab 1. Performance Analysis of Face Biometric Authentication System

These results underscore the system's effectiveness in providing secure and efficient access control through facial biometrics technology. This technology offers a robust means of authentication, enhancing the overall security of the system. Moreover, by utilizing facial recognition, the system provides a seamless user experience, minimizing the need for cumbersome authentication processes. These findings position the system as a compelling solution for organizations seeking efficient and reliable means of user authentication.

VII. CONCLUSION

After gaining a thorough understanding of the Python language, including its modules and libraries, and analyzing previous virtual assistants and their shortcomings, along with studying the Raspberry Pi and its requirements, the development of the virtual assistant integrated with a home surveillance system began.

The process involved careful selection of the most appropriate algorithms, modules, and libraries, which were then implemented into the system. Factors such as budget constraints and resource limitations were taken into account during the selection of each component.

VIII. FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

In terms of future prospects, there is ample opportunity to enhance the system with additional intelligent features and functionalities, given the ongoing advancements in this field. While the Home Surveillance System represents just one facet of the system's potential, there is scope for expansion. By incorporating devices like PIR sensors, door/window sensors, and Wi-Fi switches, the system can be seamlessly integrated with various appliances and devices, transforming an ordinary house into a fully functional smart home. For instance, Wi-Fi switches enable remote control of devices, allowing users to turn them on or off from any location. Furthermore, these switches can be endowed with intelligence by linking them to the system. For example, a Wi-Fi switch connected to the water geyser can be programmed to activate it at a designated time each morning. In this advanced setup, users may simply issue commands to execute basic tasks such as controlling lights, fans, doors, etc., eliminating the need for physical exertion. PIR sensors offer another avenue for detecting human presence in a space, with only the microphone and speaker operational in rooms where activity is detected. Overall, this technology holds promise for enhancing the quality of life for the visually impaired, making everyday household tasks more manageable and less physically demanding.

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